

Italy: the human being is under attack

ABSTRACT

On 21 April 2020 the Royal Society of Chemistry [1] published a press review on lipid nanoparticles, the heart of the new drug delivery systems. More and more tiny, more "invasive" elements that work on pharmacokinetics, based on physico-chemical properties: solubility, crystallinity, toxicity, etc. These "new" therapeutic systems, microscopic particles with a diameter of 100 nm (nanometers) visible only with particular microscopes called, CryoTEM, (electron microscopy read in cryogenic suspension), in fact these systems are the purpose of the whole, to be able to enter the body deeper and deeper.

"Man" has always wanted to replace the creator by conquering man, with the use of various methods, nano particles, transport elements to enter cells, various kinds of substances: Liposomes, Polymeric Nanoparticles, Super-magnetic, silicon, unit carbon (graphene), gold, while knowing the previous failures and the damage caused in the past.

Vaccinations in these two years of perpetual pandemic have the purpose of experimenting these transport processes, vectors of various kinds, so-called advanced therapies, regulated in 2007 (EC) No. 1394/2007, Directive 2001/83 / EC n. 726/2004, to inject, change, replace pieces of DNA. [3]

- **Terapia genica:** usata per trattare malattie causate da geni difettosi. In questo caso il "farmaco" è il DNA o RNA (si parla quindi di terapie a RNA), molecole con le quali si mira a correggere il difetto genetico direttamente all'interno delle cellule del paziente inserendo una copia corretta del gene o modificandone la sua funzione. In questo settore sono incluse anche le tecniche di editing genomico, come la CRISPR- Cas che ha recentemente vinto il premio Nobel per la Chimica. Di recente l'Ospedale Bambin Gesù di Roma ha presentato risultati interessanti alla Società Americana di Ematologia sull'uso di questa tecnica per correggere i difetti genetici alla base di talassemia e anemia falciforme. Altro esempio di terapie geniche sono i vaccini anti Covid studiati da Pfizer e Moderna, realizzati con la tecnologia mRNA.

- **Terapia cellulare:** utilizza una preparazione contenente cellule vive per ottenere un effetto terapeutico, diagnostico o preventivo. Un esempio di terapia cellulare è la Car-T, Chimeric Antigen Receptor (cellule T con recettore chimerico dell'antigene) che è un trattamento in cui i linfociti T prelevati da un paziente sono reinfusi nel suo organismo dopo essere stati modificati geneticamente in laboratorio, per aumentarne l'azione contro il tumore.

- **Ingegneria tissutale:** si basa su cellule o tessuti ottenuti in laboratorio per rigenerare, riparare o sostituire un tessuto umano, come la cute, le ossa e la cartilagine.

- **Terapie avanzate combinate,** che contengono uno o più dispositivi medici come parte integrante del farmaco.

Nel 2009 è entrato in vigore in Europa il regolamento CE n. 1394/2007 per disciplinare l'autorizzazione all'immissione in commercio di queste terapie innovative. L'approvazione di un ATMP passa attraverso il Comitato per le Terapie Avanzate (CAT) dell'EMA. Ma si tratta di terapie costose, che in alcuni casi superano il milione di euro a dose. La domanda è semplice, la risposta meno: tutto questo è sostenibile?

- Products for **Genetic therapies:** use as drugs DNA or RNA Products
- for **Cell therapy:** for therapies with live cell preparations. Products of
- **tissue engineering:** regenerate, repair, replace a fabric.
- Products of **advanced therapies:** medical devices to integrate a drug.

But have people been adequately informed? They understood what they were inoculating, accepting the own responsibility for possible damages?

The descriptions of these components are "Synthetics" and clearly for synthetics you can indicate everything. But, did the inoculates and inoculators know that the excipients mentioned in the vaccination are not suitable for human use as the data sheets of the respective producers of the complaints specify?

The people, who signed, accepted everything, for various reasons: fear, oppression, discomfort, etc., what we all know, without knowing the actual nature of the compounds.

A question arises spontaneously for everyone: are we really willing to continuously accept these new systems made of nanomedicines, nanotherapies, nanoparticles with various synthetic and technological chemicals in the near future?

Those who have the MTHFR gene mutation (C677T - A1298C) or combinations thereof are at the expense of such invasions. This mutation affects a large mass of Italians over 62% (data are 1999/2000), as well as the other races most affected, from Covid-19 with the native Americans, the Hispanics. Many thrombotic and anaphylactoid problems have hit these populations mainly due to the excipients of vaccines. [2]

FIGURE 2. Population frequency of the C677T allele of 5,10-methylenetetrahydrofolate reductase (MTHFR), by geographic area and ethnicity, 1995–1999. Data were obtained from table 1.

Link publication

[https://www.researchgate.net/publication/12524932_5_10-](https://www.researchgate.net/publication/12524932_5_10-Methylenetetrahydrofolate_Reductase_Gene_Variants_and_Congenital_Anomalies_A_HuGE_Review)

[Methylenetetrahydrofolate_Reductase_Gene_Variants_and_Congenital_Anomalies_A_HuGE_Review / link / 56a9656508aeaeb4cef954b7 / download](https://www.researchgate.net/publication/12524932_5_10-Methylenetetrahydrofolate_Reductase_Gene_Variants_and_Congenital_Anomalies_A_HuGE_Review)

Introduction

The pandemic was an opportunity to experiment with the massive use of these nano carriers, drug carriers, viruses or LNP systems. LNPs are lipid nano-particles contained in Moderna and Pfizer vaccines, through the use of the PEG excipient, to encapsulate the so-called lipid nanoparticles (LNP). To support this process, on nanomedicines, other excipients mentioned here participate, to protect the messenger mRNA, from the degradation of the nuclease, to reach the target.

These microscopic oil-like droplets, about $0.1\ \mu\text{m}$ in diameter, surround and protect the fragile mRNA during production, transport and eventual injection into the body, enter the cell by endocytosis and attach electrostatically and exit by exocytosis. The systemically administered mRNA-Lnp complexes affect the liver by binding to apolipoprotein E and are absorbed by suitable receptors in the liver.

PEG has never been found in any other vaccine in the world, this is the first time in the pharmaceutical field (Vaccinal). Similarly, to aggravate the adverse reactions, we also find the remaining excipients, **ALC-0159**, **ALC-0315**, **Lipid SM-102**, **PEG2000 DMG**, etc. According to the data sheets of the producers of these excipients, they declare from their respective technical data sheets:

Sfondo: ALC-0315 è un lipide ionizzabile che è stato utilizzato per formare nanoparticelle lipidiche per il rilascio di RNA. ALC-0315 è uno dei componenti del vaccino BNT162b2 contro SARS-CoV-2 oltre a ALC-0159, DSPC e colesterolo. Questo prodotto è solo per uso di ricerca e non per uso umano.

SM-102 è un ammino lipide ionizzabile che è stato utilizzato in combinazione con altri lipidi nella formazione di nanoparticelle lipidiche.¹ La somministrazione dell'mRNA della luciferasi in nanoparticelle lipidiche contenenti SM-102 induce l'espressione della luciferasi epatica nei topi. Le formulazioni contenenti SM-102 sono state utilizzate nello sviluppo di nanoparticelle lipidiche per la somministrazione di vaccini a base di mRNA.

Questo prodotto deve essere utilizzato solo per la ricerca. Non è inteso per uso farmacologico o diagnostico, consumo umano o per essere utilizzato in alimenti o additivi alimentari.

Are these nano-particles inserted into the "compounds" that create the adverse reactions and promote what is found in the autopsies? The carrier vectors break down on the road, before the target, or create inflammation, which, for example, in subjects affected by genetic mutations such as MTHFR, [2] promote thrombosis, ADE, due to metabolic and amino acid deficiencies, due to lack of conversion vitamin substances, such as to block, in the absence of one of the three fundamental ones, the production of antibodies.

In the presence of an enzymatic malfunction, of methionine and folate (MTHFR), which are difficult to convert, one is not ready for an immune response or solicitation, creating a violent block in the whole body, triggering a multitude of negative processes, putting in serious danger to individuals unaware of having inherited the MTHFR mutation from their parents.

A targeted preliminary investigation is a must, given the experimentation process, albeit emergency, in the interest of the life of the human being, which has been strongly hindered on all sides, to advocate a different interest, that of grasping this opportunity to make Italy the leader for advanced gene vaccinations. [5]

The even more serious thing is that the excipients mentioned are not for human use, nor for diagnosis, nor for therapy but only for research, as is publicly declared by the manufacturers of the excipients.

Questo si potrebbe fare subito, il problema è che andrebbe ad impattare su alcune risorse che poi vengono redistribuite a livello regionale e quindi c'è una contrarietà da parte delle Regioni".

I fondi per i farmaci innovativi, oncologici e non, necessitano di una revisione?

Il fatto che i vaccini in dirittura d'arrivo per il SARS-COV-2 siano di fatto delle terapie geniche, sviluppate anche grazie all'aiuto degli Stati, potrebbe far compiere quel salto culturale che permetterebbe di rendere le terapie innovative davvero accessibili, attraverso accordi tra privati e governi che inizino fin dallo sviluppo dei farmaci e non si limitino a una semplice negoziazione sul prezzo finale. In questo modo, più che un mercato sostenibile, l'Italia potrebbe diventare volano di innovazione per queste terapie.

Sommario delle principali caratteristiche dei due vaccini anti Covid ad mRNA Pfizer e Moderna estratto da Summary Product Characteristics e NEJM 8 gennaio 2021		
	MODERNA	PFIZER
Nome	COVID-19 Vaccine Moderna	Comirnaty
Composizione	Flaconcino multidose da 10(11)* dosi di 0,5ml con 100 mcgr mRNA	Flaconcino multidose da 5(6)* dosi di 0,3 mL con 30 micgr mRNA
Nanoparticelle lipidiche	Colesterolo, SM-102, DSPC, PEG2000 DMG	Colesterolo, ALC-0315, ALC-0159, DSPC
Excipienti	Potassio cloruro, Potassio diidrogeno fosfato, Sodio cloruro, Fosfato disodico diidrato, saccarosio, acqua per preparazioni iniettabili	Potassio cloruro, Potassio Diidrogeno fosfato, Sodio cloruro, Fosfato disodico diidrato, saccarosio, acqua per soluzioni iniettabili
forma farmaceutica	Congelato sospensione	Congelato da diluire con 1,8 ml di soluzione salina
Indicazione	Prevenzione della malattia Covid >= 18 anni	Prevenzione della malattia Covid >= 16 anni
Posologia	2 dosi da 0,5 ml a distanza di 28 gg	2 dosi a distanza almeno di 21 gg
Somministrazione	Intramuscolare	Intramuscolare
Controindicazioni	Ipersensibilità ai componenti	Ipersensibilità ai componenti
Ipersensibilità	Cautela per ipersensibili e disponibilità di trattamento	Cautela per ipersensibili e disponibilità di trattamento
Copatologia	Rimando se in malattia acuta febbrile	Rimando se in malattia acuta febbrile
Coagulopatie	Cautela per rischio emorragie locali	Cautela per rischio emorragie locali
Immunocompromessi	risposta possibilmente indebolita	risposta possibilmente indebolita
Durata protezione	Efficacia vista in 2 mesi, anticorpi per 4 mesi	Efficacia vista in 2 mesi, anticorpi per 2 mesi
Piena efficacia	14 giorni dopo seconda dose (42 gg dalla prima)	7 giorni dopo seconda dose (28 gg dalla prima)
Sodio	Meno di 1 millimole	Meno di 1 millimole
Gravidanza	Valutare rischio Covid/beneficio vaccino	Valutare rischio Covid/beneficio vaccino
Allattamento	Non si sa se il vaccino passa nel latte, non c'è motivo di sospendere l'allattamento	Non si sa se il vaccino passa nel latte, non c'è motivo di sospendere l'allattamento
Fertilità	Dati su animali negativi per danni	Dati su animali negativi per danni

Most important excipients of the two vaccines

Pfizer

(ALC-0315) ((4-hydroxybutyl) azanediyl) bis (hexane-6,1-diyl) bis (2-hexyldecanoate)

(ALC-0159) 2 - [(polyethylene glycol) -2000] -N, N-dithetradecylacetamide

Source: <https://www.echelon-inc.com/product/alc-0315/>

Source: <https://www.echelon-inc.com/product/alc-0159/>

Modern

SM-102 (heptadecane-9-yl 8 - {(2-hydroxyethyl) [6-oxo-6- (undecyloxy) hexyl] amino} octanoate)

1,2-dimyristoyl-rac-glycerol-3-methoxy polyethylene glycol-2000 (PEG2000 DMG)

Source: https://www.matreya.com/Products/1-2-wbrDistearoyl-wbrsn-wbrglycero-wbr3-wbrphosphorylcholine_1427.aspx

Source: <https://www.echelon-inc.com/product/dspc-180-pc/>

Discussion

Lipid nanoparticles are used as the main component of mRNA vaccines for COVID-19, these are lipid substances that attempt to keep the mRNA protected and help it arrive at target delivery.

- <https://www.Osservatorioterapieavanzate.it/terapie-avanzate/immunoterapia/car-t-sfruttare-lenanoparticelle-per-produrre-una-versione-Meno-tossica>

The current topic concerns the transport of nucleic acids (DNA and RNA) into cells through the gene therapy , on viral vectors, there are obstacles and limitations for transport, given the side effects, including immunogenetics, producing various damages and risks, with a possible lethal immune response. The critical element lies in the transfer, not only of viruses, but also of electric fields, nanomaterials and light.

Several researchers have asked themselves various questions about adverse reactions, where do these start from?

What is the cause. The elements taken into consideration are the excipients of vaccines

- <https://www.allergologico.it/news/perche-si-verificano-reazioni-anafilattiche-al-vaccino-mrnaanti-covid.html>
- <https://www.science.org/content/article/suspicious-grow-nanoparticles-pfizer-s-covid-19-vaccine-trigger-rare-allergic-reactions>

Summing up, several researchers, immunologists have come up against this problem, which directly involves vaccinations, Spike and excipients, arriving at these conclusions:

- Potential culprits of immediate hypersensitivity reactions to the Covid-19 mRNA vaccine not only PEG, in fact in the conclusions of the research we read:

"In conclusion, the culprit involved in cases of immediate mRNA vaccine reactions appears to be concentrated mainly in the LNP that makes up the envelope. Further research on this topic is crucial, as a better understanding of the mechanism underlying the adverse reaction could allow for better risk stratification and patient selection, thus increasing safety for people undergoing vaccination "

Doi 10.23822 / EurAnnACI.1764-1489.214

Source: <http://www.eurannallergyimm.com/cont/journals-articles/1043/volume-potential-culprits-immediate-hypersensitivity-reactions.asp>

- Vaccination hesitation and the "myth" about mRNA-based vaccines in Italy in the COVID-19 era: does urgency meet the main safety criteria? of facts in the conclusions of the research we read:

"Around new and simple vaccine formulations, mistrust dominates the scenario, so correct and honest information is mandatory. Medical science is never completely perfect for answering any puzzling questions about how humans can deal with terrible diseases and pandemics, which occur in a uniform way. Still, any civilized discussion of vaccines should be very respectful of the enormous efforts made by current science and technology to support the optimal solution to these concerns. Positive attitudes and trust in science are the best way to consider vaccination a safe practice. In this context, the scientific community must

expose every critical comment, in the most proactive way, to broaden a debate with the sole purpose of obtaining transparency from Big Pharma and politics, so as to guarantee citizens and public opinion. If we fully trust these fundamental keystones, then anyone can directly contribute to making our world much more enjoyable and accessible. "

DOI: 10.1002 / jmv.26922

Source: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/33666240/>

- Allergic reactions and anaphylaxis to LNP-based COVID-19 vaccines

"In line with these developments, we must also promote further research on anaphylaxis to better understand the immunopathogenesis and pathophysiology of this life-threatening condition, particularly in the context of modern genetic vaccines and nanomedicine developments. "

DOI: [10.1016 / j.ymthe.2021.01.030](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ymthe.2021.01.030)

Source: [https://www.cell.com/molecular-therapy-family/molecular-therapy/fulltext/S1525-0016\(21\)00064-](https://www.cell.com/molecular-therapy-family/molecular-therapy/fulltext/S1525-0016(21)00064-2)

[2?_ReturnURL = https% 3A% 2F% 2Flinkinghub.elsevier.com% 2Fretrieve% 2Fpii% 2FS15250016 21000642% 3Fshowall% 3Dtrue](https://www.cell.com/molecular-therapy-family/molecular-therapy/fulltext/S1525-0016(21)00064-2?_ReturnURL=https%3A%2F%2Flinkinghub.elsevier.com%2Fretrieve%2Fpii%2FS1525001621000642%3Fshowall%3Dtrue)

At the end of the documented research, we always come back with the same question, why have they never spoken or declared the excipients "Not for human use" and had an informed consent signed?

Why have they always given little consideration to the MTHFR gene mutation, which "disappeared" from the RDG020 list of rare diseases?

And why have they hindered exemptions and in-depth genetic research on MTHFR in every way?

We remind you that the same Italian prosecutors, after the suspicious deaths following the vaccines of Astra Zeneca, news of TG1Online, requesting specific genetic tests C677T - A1298C, no one has spoken about it anymore and not even about the results of the tests.

Conclusion

Modern, innovative studies and research should direct efforts not to "coercion" to speed up the timing of vaccinations for a different purpose for collective health, that is economic, but should broaden the range of comparisons and comparisons, to obtain the best result, with the lowest possible risk, close to zero.

The persistent vaccination and experimental processes, which are desired at all costs to obtain, what will never be possible, given the damage that has always been done to human beings.

These actions wish to propose and impose, a single solution for health, these advanced therapies, replacing them with the previous ones, through nano-medicines, invading the human being with experiments, passively accepted, by means of political and economic levers, not for the health of peoples.

The thing that must be clear for everyone is that no one is master of the body of others, and that all possible ways must be used, personalized treatments according to the innate constitution, one's genetic combination, far from deceit, coercion and impositions, since in this way

as there are various races, various languages, there are also various cures and solutions, each individual is a world unto himself.

The use of a good discovery is always a double-edged sword depends on the person who uses it and on the function he will want to do with it. Evolution is important, but changing the human being, going deep into smaller and smaller particles, is pure madness, this means wanting to replace the creator, ethics and science are compromised, as well as individual freedoms, sanctioned by Italian Constitution, giving way to "diabolical" economic power.

- <https://www.Osservatorioterapieavanzate.it/bioetica-e-dintorni/covid-19-il-valore-degli-studi-diinfection-umana-controllata>

Nanofilm di polibenzidina stampato elettrochimicamente su nanotubi di carbonio a parete multipla ancorate su fibre di grafite a matita per l'estrazione enantioselettiva in fase micro-solida accoppiata con rilevamento ultratraccia di d- e l-metionina

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affiliazioni + espandere

PMID: 23262195 DOI: 10.1016/j.jchromb.2012.10.010

Astratto

Viene presentato un metodo alternativo per la modifica delle fibre di grafite a matita utilizzando la tecnologia di stampa superficiale. In questo nuovo approccio, abbiamo adottato l'elettropolimerizzazione iniziata in superficie del monomero di benzidina, con l'imprinting simultaneo del modello (d- e l-metionina), su nanotubi di carbonio a parete multipla carbossilati ancorati a fibra di grafite a matita. Ciò ha prodotto una pellicola stampata ultrasottile nanostrutturata (58,3 nm) uniformemente rivestita lungo tutto il perimetro e la lunghezza della fibra di grafite a matita, per l'estrazione in fase micro-solida con una notevole capacità di adsorbimento. Lo stesso film è rivestito sulla punta esposta della fibra di grafite a matita per fungere da sensore-polimero complementare a stampa molecolare. Sia i dispositivi di estrazione che quelli di rilevamento non sono in grado di misurare il limite rigoroso (0.016ngmL(-1)) di rilevamento clinico della mutazione del gene della metilenetetraidrofolato reduttasi (MTHFR) causata da deplezione acuta di metionina, quando usato da solo. Tuttavia, sulla combinazione di entrambe le tecniche, un'analisi enantioselettiva riuscita di d- e l-metionina con eccellenti cifre analitiche di merito [limite dell'intervallo di quantificazione: 0,03-30,00 ngmL(-1), limite di rilevazione: 0,0098 ngmL(-1) (RSD=2.04, S/N=3)] potrebbe essere ottenuto senza alcun problema di contributo falso positivo non specifico e reattività crociata, in campioni reali.

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Conflict of Interest Statement

The authors declare that they have no known conflicts of interest or personal relationships that could have influenced the work reported in this document.

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